

***Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* ssp. nov. from Turkey and
Vadonia lazarevi sp. nov. from Greece (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

J. Vartanis*

Luhanova 1825, Uherský Brod, CZ - 688 01, Czech Republic

e-mail: janisvartanis@seznam.cz; giannisiv@seznam.cz

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Abstract. *Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* **ssp. nov.** is described from Turkey (Adiyaman Province). *Vadonia lazarevi* **sp. nov.** is described from Greece (Crete).

***Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* ssp. nov.**

Plate 1

Diagnosis. Body black, pronotum red, elytron black, but on its surface, there is a red spot, which occupies at least 1/3 of total area. Pronotum red, only the edges slightly black, sparsely dotted, the spaces between the dots are larger than the dots themselves. Pronotum very sparsely black-brown haired. Antennae black, thin and very short in relation to body length, compared to nominal species. And here is a very visible feature in males, where 3rd antennomeres is as long as the 5th antennomeres, where 4th and 6th antennomeres reach only 0.85% of length of 3rd and 5th antennomeres (plate 1). In addition, antennae in males shorter and their length exceeds end of elytron by only 2 antennomeres. Below we will compare this distinctive feature in nominal species *P. wachanrui wachanrui* in description. Body length of males and females: 13.0-14.0 mm.

Differential diagnosis: The new species *Purpuricenus wachanrui anatolicus* **ssp. nov.**, of genus *Purpuricenus* Dejean 1821, differs significantly from the nominal species *P. w. wachanrui* Levrat 1858. According to the original description, Levrat 1858, body

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black, antennae black, slender, each antennomeres pointing upwards, slightly swollen. Antennae in males long, significantly exceeding the length of the elytron by at least 4 or more antennomeres. 3rd and 4th antennomeres equally long, in contrast, 5th and 6th antennomeres are 1.2 times longer than the previous two antennomeres (plate 1). These two very distinctive and visible characters that distinguish it from the new species. Head, short, black, finely pubescent, covered with black-brown hairs. Pronotum black, heavily dotted, spherical, full in middle, with shiny longitudinal lines, barely pronounced, which are a result of the absence of spines. Elytra one third wider than at the base of prothorax, slightly demarcated, almost parallel, up to 2/3 of the length black, covered with very strong punctation towards the anterior part and gradually weaker towards the end. Elytra decorated with a red spot. The new species *P. w. anatolicus* **ssp. nov.** has very distinctive features that distinguish it from all similar species of entire group, such as *P. w. wachanrui* Levrat 1858 from Iran, Iraq, Syria, Turkey, Cyprus, as well as *P. zarudnianus* Semenov 1908 from Iran, *P. nanus* Semenov 1907 from Iran, *P. robusticollis* Pic 1905 from Iran and *P. persicus* Vartanis 2023 from Iran. I have all of above-listed species in my collection.

Materials. Holotypes, male, Turkey, Adıyaman Prov., Kahta env., Nemrut Dagi Mt., 2-14.VI.1996, Petr Jelínek lgt. - collection of J. Vartanis; 7 Paratypes (collection of J. Vartanis); 2 males, 2 females, Turkey mer.or., Adiyamah-Kuyucak, 8.VI.1996, M. Snížek lgt.; 1 male, 1 female, Turkey, Adıyaman Prov., Nemrut Dagi Mt., Karadut env., 15.VI.2008, Pavel Jelínek lgt.; 1 female, Turkey, Adıyaman Prov., Kahta env., Nemrut Dagi Mt., 2-14.VI.1996, Petr Jelínek lgt.

Bionomy. Imagoes were found on flowers *Echinops* sp. (*Asteracea*).

Etymology. The new species was named after name of its area in eastern Turkey.

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Plate 1

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***Vadonia lazarevi* sp. nov.**

Plate 2, 3, 4

Diagnosis. Body, limbs, pronotum and antennae are black, elytra brownish-yellow. Antennae slender, reaching up to 2/3 of length of the elytron in males and up to 1/2 of length of the elytron in females. Limbs, short and strong, hind and middle femurs evenly covered with hair. Hind tibia with one spine. Feet of hind tarsi only partially brushed. Pronotum, black, spherical, very densely finely punctate, with a longitudinal smooth groove in middle, yellow-brown hairs, very dense and very prominent towards the outside. Elytron, brownish-yellow, each elytron with a smaller black spot in middle. The punctation of elytron is very dense and fine, in 1/3 very distinct yellow-brown pubescence, in other 2/3 towards the apex glabrous, without pubescence. Elytra very short, stocky, strongly arched longitudinally, in the last fifth narrowing backwards. From scutellum along seam, slightly expanded indistinct black striations in males and more expanded in females. Body length in males: 13-14 mm, in females 13-15 mm.

Plate 2

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Differential diagnosis: I would like to analyze the large group of *Vadonia* species that occur in Greece. There are 18 species of the genus *Vadonia* in Greece and the new species *V. lazarevi* is 19th in order. Below I am inserting a map of all Greek species and species in blue frame fall into the group where males show only 1 spine on the hind tibia. There are 7 species in total with one spine. These 7 species are diametrically different from the new species *V. lazarevi*, they are larger, they belong to the group of large species, such as *V. bisignata bisignata*, *V. bisignata laurae*, *V. samosensis*, other species such as *V. dojranensis dojranensis*, *V. d. mahri* and *V. moesiaca* occur only in north of Greece and last species *V. monostigma* extends from Turkey, only to the north-eastern part of Greece. Moreover, none of these species shows a visible sign like new species *V. lazarevi*, where there is a black spot on the elytron, which extends from the scutellum and extends along elytron seam. Moreover, all penises in males were compared with all Greek species that I have in my collection. In addition to all the Greek species, I have the entire genus *Vadonia*.

Materials. Holotypes, male, Greece, Crete Isl., Idi Mt., Fourfouras, V.2024, Alexis Vartanis lgt. - collection of J. Vartanis; 15 Paratypes (collection of J. Vartanis); 11 males, 4 females, Greece, Crete Isl., Idi Mt., Fourfouras, V.2024, A. Vartanis lgt.

Bionomy. The adults were found on flowers of *Euphorbia* sp. The new subspecies is endemic of Crete and a single taxon of the genus in the island (plate 2).

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to a colleague and longhorn beetle specialist Maxim A. Lazarev (Free Economic Society of Russia, Moscow).

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Vadonia genus, species occurring in Greece.

- 1) *V.albanica* Vartanis 2019 - HT,PT, GR,(Makedonia D,Ipiros). 2) *V.bisignata laurae* Pesarini & Sabbadini 2007 - GR,(Thessalia, E). 3) *V.bisignata bisignata* Brullé 1832 - GR,(Peloponnissos, E). 4) *V.dojranensis dojranensis* Holzschuh 1984 - GR,(Makedonia kentriki). 5) *V.dojranensis mahri* Holzschuh 1985 - PT, GR,(Makedonia anatoliki,Thraki). 6) *V.gusmii* Pesarini & Sabbadini 2010 - GR,(Peloponnissos, E). 7) *V.insidiosa* Holzschuh 1984 - GR,(Thessalia, E). 8) *V.klichai* Vartanis 2017 - HT,PT, GR,(Pindos Mt.,Ipiros, Corfu Isl., E). 9) *V.mainoldii* Pesarini & Sabbadini 2004 - GR,(Makedonia W., E). 10) *V.moesiaca* K.-J. Daniel 1891 - GR,(Makedonia W.,Ipiros). 11) *V.monostigma* Ganglbauer 1882 - GR,(Makedonia A.,Thraki) 12) *V.parnassensis* Pic 1925 - GR,(Sterea Ellada-Parnasos Mt., E). 13) *V.samosensis* Vartanis 2016 - HT,PT - GR,(Samos Isl., E). 14) *V.unipunctata dalmatina* Müller 1907 - GR,(Makedonia). 15) *V.unipunctata ikariaensis* Danilevsky & Vartanis 2015 - HT,PT, - GR,(Ikaria Isl., E). 16) *V.unipunctata makedonica* Holzschuh 1989 - PT, GR,(Makedonia anatoliki,kentriki,Thraki, E). 17) *V.unipunctata ohridensis* Holzschuh 1987 - PT, GR,(Makedonia W.,Ipiros). 18) *V.unipunctata unipunctata* Fabricius 1787 - GR,(Olympos Mt.). 19) *Vadonia lazarevi* Vartanis 2026 - HT,PT, - GR,(Creta Isl., E). HT-Holotypus, PT-Paratypus E - Endemic species of Greece.

Plate 3

Species in the blue box are males that have only 1 spine on the hind tibia, compared to species not in the blue box, where males have 2 spines on the hind tibia.

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Elytra entirely yellow, the tips not blackened, as in all other species below. The new species is endemic to the island of Crete. This is a smaller species, 13-14mm.	Elytra entirely yellow, the tips not blackened, as in all other species below. In some specimens a black spot extends from the scutellum, along the seam, to the middle of the elytron.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, probably one of the largest in the entire genus, where individuals exceed 20 mm. It is an endemic species for the Peloponnese peninsula.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, where individuals reach 17-19mm. The destination of occurrence is in central Greece, in the region of Thessaly, it is not widespread elsewhere.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, the size can exceed 20 mm. The photo shows the Holotype . This is an endemic species of the island of Samos.
Vadonia lazarevi sp.n. Creta Isl.	Vadonia lazarevi sp.n. Creta Isl.	V.bisignata bisignata Peloponnissos	V.bisignata laurae Central Greece	Vadonia samosensis Samos Isl.
Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. This is a large species, the size can reach 16-18 mm. Occurrence only in eastern Macedonia in northern Greece. This is a Paratypus , from the collection of the Vienna Museum.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. It is a medium-sized species, around 13-14 mm. Destination of occurrence in Greece only in the north, throughout the region of Macedonia.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. It is a medium-sized species, around 14-16mm. The destination of occurrence in Greece is very limited, only in central Macedonia, very rarely.	Elytra yellow, but at the end of the tips they are always blackened, both in males and females. It is a medium-sized species, around 14-16mm. Destination of occurrence in Greece, mainly in the eastern part of Macedonia and Thrace, much more abundant than the previous species.	Elytra completely black, this is a rare aberration of the species. In the photo Paratypus from my collection. Destination of occurrence in Greece, in the eastern region of Macedonia and Thrace.
Vadonia monostigma Macedonia E	Vadonia moesiaca Macedonia	V.dojran.dojranensis Macedonia C	V.dojranensis mahri Macedonia E	V.dojranensis mahri Macedonia E

Plate 4

The 8 species below, including the new species *Vadonia lazarevi* from island Crete, have only (1 spine) on hind tibia in males, whole other species in Greece have (2 spines). Below I have shown a comparison of elytron with each other, in addition 3 species are Holotypus and Paratypus from my collection and 1 specimen from Vienna Museum.

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